

Homeostatic (allostatic, teleonomic) efficiency and vitality

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ABSTRACT

This Opinion Article provides a brief overview of the environment – animal relationship as a foundation for describing *vitality* as a holistic outcome of agency and environmental mastery. The account draws on the ecological view of animals as dynamic adaptive networks that convert energy and information into order, complexity and predictions within an animal's structures and functions. In accord with the Extended Evolutionary Synthesis, actions of the animal extend beyond self-maintenance to provide gifts to conspecific and ecological communities, as well as to offspring. These self- and other-focused outcomes are facilitated by the *efficiency* with which the capture and use of energy and information are attuned to environmental dynamics. A challenge for animal and health sciences is to describe how well individuals are mastering their environment: are they surviving or thriving? In the early 1900s, before control theory proposed feedback pathways drive physiological variables towards fixed set points, many physiologists including Walter Cannon recognised the importance of dynamic changes, adaptation, and complexity in enabling *relative* stability of the internal environment: the outcome Cannon described as homeostasis. Cannon and Hoskins suggested that the *efficiency* with which animals maintain homeostasis in the face of environmental challenges could provide an index of vitality. As a holistic outcome of coherent internal functions and external harmony, it is suggested that Hoskins' and Cannon's concept of *homeostatic efficiency* has current-day utility as a measure of the animal's mastery of its environment: its vitality. The outcome is agnostic of underlying pathways and can equally be described as allostatic or teleonomic efficiency. Hence, the term homeostatic efficiency does not imply rigidity or an underlying set-point model of regulation. The characteristics of day-to-day variations in products such as milk yield, body weight, egg output, and feed intake are currently interpreted as indicators of resilience. From the ecological view of the animal – environment dynamic, it is suggested that homeostatic efficiency provides a holistic indicator of vitality that encompasses the tribulations of daily life and resilience in adversity. This shifts studies of day-to-day fluctuations from a focus on external causes towards descriptions of the animal's capacity to maintain coherence and harmony. Homeostatic efficiency complements other holistic indicators of vitality including behavioural indicators of affective states, qualitative behavioural assessment, fluctuating asymmetry, and functional and structural entropy (including the microbiome).

Keywords: vitality, homeostatic efficiency, homeostasis, allostasis, resilience, teleonome, competence, environmental mastery, wellbeing

Harnessing energy and information

49 Form and function tend to persist across the life of the organism and to be propagated into
50 future generations. Schrödinger noted that persistence runs counter to the tendency for disorder
51 (entropy) to increase over time (Nicholson, 2025). Order, Prigogine suggested, is created by the
52 organism's capacity to "dissipate" energy (Goldbeter, 2018). Free energy in materials – the energy
53 available to do work - is used to create and maintain form and function in a state far from
54 thermodynamic equilibrium through a process of self-organisation that Varela et al. (1974) termed
55 autopoiesis. Prigogine's "dissipative structures" not only capture energy, they also capture
56 information. The application of information theory to biology has led to the description of
57 information capture as a process that reduces the organism's uncertainty about the conditions and
58 events it anticipates experiencing. Free information in events and conditions in the environment –
59 the information available to reduce uncertainty – is used to construct predictions of future
60 experience through a process Friston et al. (2010) termed active inference. In a cyclical manner,
61 expectations such as presence of nutrients near a microorganism or the imminent arrival of the
62 feed truck in a cow barn are updated by sensations that are in turn modified by actions of the
63 organism (Kristiansen & Fernö, 2020). Updating through cycles of prediction and action form a
64 process of approximate Bayesian inference (Friston et al., 2017). A capacity for active inference is
65 not restricted to organisms with brains but is present in all life forms (Lyon, 2015). So important is
66 the capture of information that numerous authors have concluded life is fundamentally a cognitive
67 process (e.g. Ball, 2023; Goodwin, 1978; Lyon, 2025). A capacity to predict patterns (i.e. to reduce
68 uncertainty) improves access to resources and reduces exposure to harms. Poor prediction and
69 control lead to stress (Weiss, 1972). Some predictions are prepackaged in phylogenetic history
70 and more proximally in genomic and epigenomic inheritances that guide development of structures
71 and functions during ontogeny. Thus, capacity to capture resources and recognise patterns is
72 canalised by inheritance. Adaptations to the inherited package during the organism's life update
73 the map (model) of information and resource dynamics of the environment (Conant & Ashby,
74 1970). Within the constraints of inheritance, adaptations and learning across a lifetime tune the
75 organism to fit a subset of all possible environments - its preferred niche.

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Organism – environment relationship

77 The dissipation of energy and reduction of uncertainty not only tunes the organism to the
78 dynamics of its environment, it also generates new information and material resources for other
79 organisms. This dynamic interplay between organism and environment was described by Von
80 Uexküll (1926) as a function-circle and subsequently by Patten (1982) as constituting a
81 fundamental unit of biology, the environ. Patten described the outputs of the environ as its
82 effectance on other organisms and the ecological networks it participated in. Patten's effectance
83 was a precursor of Niche Construction Theory and the Extended Evolutionary Synthesis (EES)
84 (Laland et al., 2015). Development of these theories represented a shift in the concept of the
85 animal - environment relationship from a duality comprised of external Newtonian forces producing
86 changes in a reactive organism towards a model of co-construction between a dynamic niche and
87 the prospective actions of the organism (Fultot & Turvey, 2019; Wemelsfelder, 1997). Actions that
88 made "hard" changes to the niche through engineering and "soft" changes through culture were
89 recognised as non-genetic aspects of inheritance that combine with genetic inheritance to
90 influence persistence across generations (Jablonka & Lamb, 2007). In the ecological view, the
91 influence of effectances extended beyond offspring to include conspecifics, the ecological
92 community, and the project of life on earth.

93 Gibson (1977) described aspects of the niche that afford opportunities for action as
94 affordances. Gibson's proposal was expanded by Turvey and others to suggest that action is
95 afforded not only by macroscopic physical structures like a handle on a cup but also by molecular
96 properties that provide opportunities for action for example by the immune system (Tauber, 2017).
97 Canalisation limits the repertoire of affordances an organism can "grasp". A property of affordances

98 proposed by Gibson was their potential "for good or ill". This quality linked affordances to the
99 concept of valence in psychology. Bacteria and higher organisms exhibit attraction and avoidance
100 to various conditions and events in their environments (Lyon & Kuchling, 2021). Although the
101 processing of information through a hierarchy of networks in more complex organisms can
102 generate properties such as sentience, consciousness and awareness of subjective experiences,
103 organisms from microbes to humans embody the same heuristic. Valence guides actions and
104 actions modify valence. Affordance and valence are not fixed properties of the environment but
105 subjective changeable qualities that emerge through the dynamic of the organism - environment
106 relationship (Lyon & Kuchling, 2021).

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The contribution of functions

108 The a priori predictions made by genetic and non-genetic inheritances cannot anticipate the full
109 range of environmental variation each newborn might experience. Thus, the forms and functions
110 encoded in genetic inheritance must be tuned and adapted by each newborn as it progresses
111 along its life course. Functions overlap in their contributions to daily life and are not delineated by
112 clear boundaries (Bergelson et al., 2021). In broad brush terms, a farm animal is endowed with
113 functions such as sensation, affect, cognition, learning, locomotion, behaviour, social interaction,
114 digestion, defence, repair, operation of the microbiome, and so on. Development of functions
115 commences before and accelerates after birth (Mellor, 2019) in many instances passing through
116 a sensitive period when tuning can be strongly guided by environmental experiences (Wiesel,
117 1982). Maturation of functions is described as the development of functional competence (Špinka
118 & Wemelsfelder, 2011). The rate of maturation of individual functions can differ across the
119 developmental trajectory and extend beyond sensitive periods to continue throughout life.

120 An important distinction lies between what a function can do such as make decisions (e.g. to
121 act or not to act) and the specific environmental context during which it is expressed (which branch
122 of this maze do I go down next). An example is provided by the immune system. The animal
123 acquires before or soon after birth an inheritance of maternal antibodies which, based on the
124 mother's experience, prepares the offspring for the antigenic encounters it is likely to face. Over
125 subsequent weeks the neonate's own immune functions mature to replace the maternal
126 inheritance with a new repertoire of receptors operating within networks of white blood cells. The
127 networks are tuned to recognise molecular structures experienced by the young animal that pose
128 threats or benefits. Activities of the networks provide defence, promote beneficial organisms in
129 the microbiome, and initiate turnover and repair of aged and damaged tissues. The targets of this
130 immune competence vary between individuals and across the life course and can include
131 molecular structures newly synthesised by humans that have never previously existed on earth
132 (Tauber, 2017). Thus, the object of action is distinct from the capacity to act. Similarly, through the
133 capacity for associative learning, an animal can link novel sequences of events not previously
134 experienced by the species during evolutionary history. The capacity to learn novel associations
135 is implemented in the design of virtual fencing technology, automatic milking systems, and many
136 other aspects of the human - animal interface (Lee et al., 2018). Humans can make new
137 affordances upon which animals can act.

138

Environmental mastery

139 This promiscuity of functions to operate across a range of contexts is nonetheless constrained.
140 The affordance of straw for nest building may be greater than plastic strips, and certain sequences
141 of notes are more easily learned by chicks as they acquire skills in song-making (James & Sakata,
142 2017). Competence acquired by the individual broadens the range of conditions amenable to
143 survival and the range of environmental perturbations the individual can accommodate (Špinka,
144 2019). Specific skills acquired as competence increases, for example the skill to navigate a maze,
145 are an open-ended set (Špinka & Wemelsfelder, 2011). Within the time limits and developmental
146 constraints of its own lifetime, an individual is only able to acquire a subset of the skills available

147 to its species. White (1959) introduce the concept of competence to describe mastery of the
148 environment as the outcome achieved through expression of agency. Environmental mastery is a
149 core feature of wellbeing (Colditz, 2022; Ryff et al., 2021). Beneath this broad framework lies the
150 need to identify practical approaches that provide pathways for improving competence in farm
151 animals (Rault et al., 2025; Špinka, 2019; Špinka & Wemelsfelder, 2011).

152 **Measuring vitality as homeostatic efficiency**

153 Can we tell how well the animal is mastering its environment? Is it competent? Is it surviving or
154 thriving? In a recent paper, Wilkins et al. (2026) examined the question through the lens of
155 teleonomy. The purposes which animals strive to fulfil, the authors noted, has a long history of
156 enquiry in philosophy and biology. Fulfilling purposes, the authors suggest, is the pathway to
157 success. In the Modern Synthesis of evolutionary theory, the purpose of evolved functions is to
158 enable persistence through survival of the individual so it can transmit genes to offspring. In the
159 EES, hard and soft contributions of the individual to its community and to the ecosystem are
160 additional agents of transgenerational persistence. Wilkins et al. (2026) propose the term
161 *teleonome* to describe the repertoire of forms, functions and environmental affordances that enable
162 the animal to fulfil its purposes. The teleonome, the authors suggest provides a foundation for
163 describing the biology of animal welfare. This important paper serves as a timely reminder of the
164 value of continually updating the biological principles brought to the study of animal welfare.

165 Vitality in daily life - how well the animal is mastering its environment - is a question that has
166 been posed in various forms for many years. Following Claude Bernard's pioneering work on the
167 tendency for animals to buffer their internal environment from external changes, Walter Cannon
168 (Cannon, 1929) described the stabilised outcome as homeostasis. At the turn of the 20th Century,
169 physiologists recognised that this stability was relative: variables like glucose and heart rate moved
170 through a range of values (Cannon, 1929, 1935). The relative stability of the internal environment
171 depended on a capacity for dynamic changes and adaptation (Abrahams, 1907; Allbutt, 1912;
172 Cannon, 1929, 1935; Henderson, 1927; Richet, 1900). Adaptive and pathological changes could
173 lead to physiological variables settling at values displaced from normal (Abrahams, 1907; Allbutt,
174 1912; Hoskins, 1931). Dynamic changes could be anticipatory: in the face of a threat the autonomic
175 nervous system prepared the animal for fight or flight (reviewed by Bechtel & Bich, 2025). Cannon's
176 contemporary at Harvard University, Roy Hoskins (1931) proposed that the *efficiency* with which
177 the animal could maintain homeostasis during a range of tests could provide a "mathematical
178 'homeostatic index' ... expressing the general 'vitality' of any given subject ... derived algebraically
179 from a fairly large number of weighted subindices" (emphasis in original, p 682). Cannon (1935)
180 enthusiastically adopted Hoskins proposal. Hoskins and Cannon recognised that they did not know
181 in detail the processes through which homeostasis was maintained. Their focus on the outcome,
182 vitality, was in line with Bernard (1865)'s earlier advice that ". . . physiologists are inclined to
183 acknowledge a harmonious and pre-established unity in an organized body, all of whose partial
184 actions are interdependent and mutually generative. We really must learn, then, that if we break
185 up a living organism by isolating its different parts, it is only for the sake of ease in experimental
186 analysis, and by no means in order to conceive them separately. Indeed, when we wish to ascribe
187 to a physiological quality its value and true significance, we must always refer to this whole and
188 draw conclusions only to its effects in the whole" (p.89). In part due to lack of molecular knowledge,
189 Cannon and other organicists of the era were interested in the goals of physiological regulation,
190 not just the means (Bechtel & Bich, 2025). Vitality was an aspect of this focus.

191 A later addition to Cannon's concept of homeostasis was the model developed in control theory
192 that feedback provided a mechanism to drive physiological values towards a fixed point
193 (Rosenblueth et al., 1943). The set point model of regulation became entrenched in physiological
194 textbooks to such an extent that Sterling and Eyer (1988) needed to break the model by re-
195 emphasising the importance of dynamic predictive and adaptive changes and coin a new term -
196 allostasis (Bechtel & Bich, 2025). The concept of allostasis provides an entry point to the study of

197 physiological regulation as a network process within complex adaptive systems (Lipsitz, 2002)
198 under the heuristic of active inference (Barrett et al., 2016).

199 **Vitality encompasses daily tribulations and resilience in adversity**

200 The dynamic stability of trajectories such as daily milk yield, body weight, egg output, and feed
201 intake have been described in recent years as indicators of *resilience* (Berghof et al., 2019; Colditz
202 & Hine, 2016; Friggens et al., 2017; Mancin et al., 2026; Scheffer et al., 2018). Following the
203 terminology of Hoskins and Cannon, these whole-animal outcomes can be understood to be
204 measures of homeostatic efficiency. The outcomes are agnostic of the mechanisms supporting
205 their expression. Indeed, as anticipated by early 20th Century physiologists, complexity in
206 structures and pathways is a resource that broadens the animal's capacity to accommodate
207 environmental perturbations and adapt to environmental change (Colditz et al., 2023). Complexity
208 such as metabolic flexibility (Rauw et al., 2025) can provide alternative pathways to an outcome
209 such as milk yield or body growth. From this pluralist perspective, the efficiency with which system
210 integrity is maintain provides a metric of success in maintaining dynamic balance with the
211 environment whether we consider the underlying processes to conform to Cannon's concept of
212 dynamic agencies maintaining homeostasis, the outdated model of set-point homeostasis, or
213 newer models such as dynamic allostasis and teleonomic fulfilment. To this end, homeostatic
214 (*sensu* Hoskins and Cannon), allostatic, and teleonomic *efficiency* can be consider equivalent
215 descriptors of vitality. In common usage, the concept of resilience has a strong association with
216 adversity. In accord with Hoskins' and Cannon's usage, day-to-day variability in trajectories such
217 as milk yield, body weight, and feed intake may be better described as indicators of vitality rather
218 than resilience. Vitality encompasses the tribulations of daily life as well as resilience in adversity.
219 A more detailed account of the history and contemporary application of these concepts is provided
220 in an upcoming publication (Colditz, 2026).

221 **System efficiency is more than milk and action**

222 The efficiency of maintaining system integrity entails more than the frugal conversion of
223 materials into milk and information into action. It describes the efficiency with which the organism
224 maintains competence and capacity to fulfil the activities necessary to be, say, "like a cow" (Wilkins
225 et al., 2026). Efficiency declines as material and cognitive resources are diverted from cow-ness
226 activities towards stress responses, with a consequent decline in internal coherence of functions
227 and external harmony of actions with environmental dynamics (Goodwin, 2001; Xiong & Garfinkel,
228 2023). The animal slips from a state of proactive mutualism with its surrounds towards reactive
229 objecthood (Colditz, 2018). The diversion of metabolic and cognitive attention leaves a signature
230 in system dynamics that provides additional holistic indicators of system integrity and vitality.

231 **Indicators of system integrity and vitality**

232 In accord with Prignone's description of organisms as dissipative structures, the efficiency of
233 capturing and distributing energy and information is enhanced by fractal complexity within
234 structures and processes (Goldberger et al., 2002; West, 2021). Structural fractal complexity is
235 seen in airways, blood and lymph vasculatures, and bone trabeculae among others. Temporal
236 fractal complexity is seen in heart rate variability, respiratory sinus arrhythmia, circadian
237 trajectories of body temperature and cortisol, and some behavioural activities, with a decrease in
238 complexity observed during stress and ageing (Alados et al., 1996; Cohen et al., 2022; Hahn et
239 al., 1992; Hahn, 1999; Lipsitz, 2004; MacIntosh et al., 2011; Maria et al., 2004). More generally,
240 an increase in disorder (entropy) in structures and functions including the microbiome (Mancin et
241 al., 2026) provides a holistic measure of physiological integrity and its inverse physiological
242 dysregulation (Cohen et al., 2025; Cummings et al., 2025). Prepathological change and allostatic
243 load are examples of disorder. Other holistic indicators include: fluctuating asymmetry in bilateral

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Figure 1. Mastering the dynamics of energy and information through competence of biological functions enables vitality. The lack of clear boundaries between domains is illustrated by overlapping ellipses. The number of functions, promoters, skills, contexts and indicators is open ended (*n...*). The goals of persistence are mediated by agents which act with tempos that range from moment to moment (affect) to transgenerational intervals (genes). QBA: Qualitative Behavioural Assessment.

252 structures of the body plan (Carvalho et al., 2026; Graham et al., 2010); behaviours embodying
253 affective states (Keeling et al., 2021); and the whole-of-animal status embodied in demeanour and
254 behaviour as assessed by qualitative behavioural assessment (QBA) (Wemelsfelder et al., 2001).
255 After a long career at the forefront of analytical physiology and complex systems theory, Brian
256 Goodwin drew inspiration from Françoise Wemelsfelder's work on QBA to illustrate the need and
257 potential for a "Science of Qualities" to describe holistic outcomes in animals and ecosystems
258 (Goodwin, 1999; Goodwin, 2001). Further refinement of methods to assess vitality and
259 environmental mastery will complement progress made in recent years in operationalising the
260 holistic animal welfare concepts of "quality of life" (Reid et al., 2022; Vigors et al., 2021), "a life
261 worth living" (Mellor, 2016; Webster, 2016; Yeates, 2011), "a good life" (Edgar et al., 2013; FAWC,
262 2009; Rowe & Mullan, 2022), "dynamic integrity" (Arndt et al., 2022; Arndt et al., 2024; Colditz et
263 al., 2023; Colditz, 2023; Ohl & van der Staay, 2012; Verhoog, 2000), and "harmony" (Colditz, 2026;
264 Hughes, 1976; Hurnik, 1988). Hoskins' and Cannon's concept of homeostatic efficiency should
265 make an important contribution to this field.

266 Figure 1 provides a diagrammatic summary of the paper. Paradoxically and frustratingly, the
267 mercurial character of biological functions means that precise definitions with strict boundaries can
268 often hinder rather than advance understanding (Bergelson et al., 2021). A word picture crafted in
269 figurative language follows in the hope it may provide additional perspective.

270

271 **Epigram**

272 Life is not a *thing* that persists, but a *process* that insists: a metabolic engine fuelled by energy,
273 and a cognitive process that turns surprise into meaning.

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275 **Limerick**

276 A cow is a whirlpool of flow,
277 Making patterns that fractally grow.
278 With senses gleaning
279 Her niche's meaning
280 She's more than the milk she can show.

281

282 **Haiku**

283 Deep flow, not a thing,
284 Seeking sense in shifting light,
285 Agency takes form.

286

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295

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